

Electrochemical Behaviour of 3-Methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-ones

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Manuscript received 18 June 1992, revised 13 March 1993, accepted 27 May 1993

Electrochemical reduction of 3-methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-ones has been carried out in Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH^{*} range of 1.66–9.66. All the compounds give single, well-defined, diffusion-controlled, irreversible reduction wave at d.m.e. while at HMDE one cathodic peak is observed at low scan rates and two cathodic peaks at high scan rates in acidic solutions and a single cathodic peak is observed in alkaline solutions at all scan rates. The products of electrolysis have been characterised and a plausible mechanism of electroreduction has been suggested.

A survey of literature revealed that 2-isoxazolin-5-ones and isoxazoles possess various types of biological activities¹ and this activity is found to depend on the pattern of their redox behaviour. In view of this, the electrochemical behaviour of the title compounds has been studied and the results are presented in this paper.

The compounds investigated are 1a–e.

- 1a, R = H 1d, R = OC₂H₅
b, R = CH₃ e, R = Cl
c, R = OCH₃

Results and Discussion

Polarography : The compounds (1a–e) exhibit a single well-defined four-electron reduction wave in the pH range 1.66–9.66. The observed linear dependence of the limiting current on $h^{1/2}$ (mercury column height) and [depolariser] suggests the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. The low temperature coefficient percentage (1.05–1.40%) of

the limiting current further supports the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ values towards more negative potentials with increase in concentration of the depolariser suggests the irreversible nature of the wave. This is further confirmed by the semi-log plots². The pH^{*} (1.66–6.66) dependence of $E_{1/2}$ indicated the participation of protons in the reduction process which suggests that the fast proton transfer precedes the main electrode process. Thus, the reduction mechanism shown in Scheme 1 may be proposed. At pH^{*} values 7.66–9.66, the $E_{1/2}$ becomes independent of pH. This means that protons do not take part in the reduction process. The position of the wave on the potential axis together with the reports made in the literature³ for the reduction of azo³ and hydrazone linkage⁴ and other observations⁵, indicate that the wave is attributed to the reduction of azo group in hydrazone form. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Cyclic voltammetry : Cyclic voltammetry at hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) shows that the compounds exhibit two cathodic peaks at high scan rates (100–400 mV s⁻¹) and one cathodic peak is observed in alkaline solutions

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON $E_{1/2}$ AND WAVE HEIGHT

Concn. = 1×10^{-3} M, Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide 50 % (v/v)

pH	Half-wave potential V vs SCE					Wave height (μ A)				
	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e
1.66	0.54	0.58	0.60	0.61	0.50	8.1	9.1	6.5	7.8	6.8
2.66	0.69	0.73	0.75	0.75	0.64	7.8	9.0	6.3	7.5	6.0
3.66	0.75	0.79	0.81	0.84	0.70	7.0	8.0	5.4	6.5	5.0
4.66	0.84	0.89	0.91	0.92	0.79	5.9	6.3	3.9	6.3	4.1
5.66	0.96	1.00	1.03	1.00	0.91	3.9	5.0	3.0	4.7	2.7
6.66	1.05	1.09	1.11	1.10	1.01	2.4	4.9	2.5	3.6	2.0
7.66	1.10	1.15	1.17	1.16	1.06	1.5	2.9	2.3	3.0	1.7
8.66	1.10	1.15	1.17	1.16	1.06	1.2	2.4	1.8	2.5	1.2

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS OF COMPOUNDS 1a-e AT pH 3.66

Concn. = 1×10^{-3} M, Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide 50% (v/v)

Compd. no.	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ Δ pH	α_s	Number of proton (p)	$\times 10^6$ D $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	$\times 10^3$ I^*	k_{th}^0 cm s^{-1}	ΔG^0 kcal mol^{-1}
1a	0.090	0.45	0.74	2.56	3.9	1.60×10^{-7}	16.6
b	0.091	0.49	0.73	3.35	4.4	3.87×10^{-8}	17.5
c	0.091	0.43	0.71	1.53	3.0	6.72×10^{-8}	17.1
d	0.097	0.43	0.79	2.21	3.6	4.89×10^{-8}	17.3
e	0.093	0.43	0.77	1.31	2.8	3.92×10^{-7}	16.1

$$* I = i_d / \text{cm}^{2/3} t^{1/6}$$

Scheme 1. Reduction pattern in acidic solution.

at all scan rates. But in contrast to this only a single wave is observed in dc polarographic studies in the entire pH* range (1.66–9.66). The two cathodic peaks observed in acidic solutions at high scan rates suggest that the reduction takes place in two steps. Further the two peaks observed in CVM only at high scan rates indicate that these steps are quite fast. This is probably the reason for the presence of a single wave instead of two waves in dc polarography. The diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction is supported by the linear plot i_p (the peak current) versus $v^{1/2}$ passing through the origin. The absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan suggests irreversible nature of the reduction. However, a cathodic peak during anodic cycle is observed in acidic solutions. Such peaks known as inverted peaks are reported in literature⁶⁻⁸ for other compounds also and these probably arise either due to movement of mercury electrode surface as a result of uneven drop polarisation (similar to polarographic maximum) or due to inhibition of electrode reaction as a consequence of coverage of the electrode surface by a product of the electrode reaction^{6,7,9}

TABLE 3—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS **1a–e** AT pH 3.66Concn. = 1×10^{-3} M, Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide 50% (v/v)

Compd. no.	Scan rate V s ⁻¹	$-E_{pc_1}$ V	$-E_{pc_{II}}$ V	$-E_{pc_{lim}}$ V	i_{pc_1} μ A	$i_{pc_{II}}$ μ A	$i_{pc_{lim}}$ μ A
1a	0.010	1.01	—	0.85	2.50	—	0.40
	0.020	1.04	—	0.85	3.50	—	0.55
	0.050	1.06	—	0.86	5.50	—	0.90
	0.100	1.09	1.25	0.89	7.75	8.70	1.25
	0.200	1.14	1.29	0.92	11.25	12.60	1.80
	0.300	1.48	1.34	0.95	13.70	15.35	2.20
b	0.010	1.05	—	0.80	3.80	—	1.00
	0.020	1.08	—	0.80	5.35	—	1.45
	0.050	1.10	—	0.79	8.35	—	2.20
	0.100	1.13	1.30	0.83	11.80	11.95	3.15
	0.200	1.17	1.35	0.85	17.10	17.30	4.60
	0.300	1.22	1.40	0.88	20.80	21.15	5.70
c	0.010	1.08	—	0.84	2.30	—	1.10
	0.020	1.10	—	0.84	3.35	—	1.50
	0.050	1.13	—	0.84	5.05	—	2.40
	0.100	1.16	1.33	0.88	7.15	5.90	3.40
	0.200	1.21	1.38	0.90	10.40	8.55	5.00
	0.300	1.26	1.43	0.93	12.65	10.55	6.05
d	0.010	1.07	—	0.85	3.00	—	1.05
	0.020	1.10	—	0.85	4.35	—	1.44
	0.050	1.13	—	0.86	6.70	—	2.30
	0.100	1.15	1.34	0.90	9.30	8.90	3.30
	0.200	1.20	1.37	0.91	13.95	13.10	4.80
	0.300	1.24	1.41	0.94	17.60	15.95	5.75
e	0.010	0.96	—	0.70	3.50	—	1.40
	0.020	0.99	—	0.70	4.90	—	1.95
	0.050	1.01	—	0.70	7.70	—	3.10
	0.100	1.03	1.18	0.73	10.85	9.95	4.35
	0.200	1.08	1.23	0.76	15.80	14.40	6.30
	0.300	1.12	1.27	0.79	19.25	17.55	7.70

The second possibility is ruled out since there is no increase in peak intensity with increase in scan rate. Since a significant polarographic maximum is observed for these compounds under experimental conditions, inverted peak is therefore due to the movement of the electrode surface. This is further substantiated by the fact that neither an inverted peak in the cyclic voltammogram nor a maximum in the polarographic reduction wave has been observed in 0.1 M NaOH solution. The cyclic voltammetric data of compounds **1a–e** are presented in Tables 3 and 4 and some typical cyclic voltammograms of 3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-one are shown in Fig. 1 at a scan rate of 0.100 V s⁻¹.

Millicoulometry : Millicoulometric experiments were carried out in Britton-Robinson buffers

containing 50% (v/v) dimethylformamide. The number of electrons involved in the reduction is found to be four. The results are presented in Table 5.

Controlled potential electrolysis : The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in a Lingane H-type cell. A large pool of mercury was used as the cathode at the bottom of the larger compartment and a similar pool of mercury at the bottom of the smaller compartment served as the anode. The cathode compartment contained 10 ml of 0.01 M 3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-one, 40 ml of DMF, 10 ml of 1.0 M KCl and 40 ml of buffer (pH 4.1). A potential of -1.1 V was applied and maintained by the manual control of the output from the battery. Progress of the electrolysis was followed by recording

TABLE 4—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF COMPOUNDS **1a-e** AT pH 7.66

Concn. = 1×10^{-3} M, Medium aqueous dimethylformamide 50% (v/v)			
Compd. no.	Scan rate $V s^{-1}$	$-E_{pc}$ V	i_{pc} μA
1a	0.010	1.47	1.50
	0.020	1.50	2.10
	0.050	1.53	3.30
	0.100	1.55	4.65
	0.200	1.59	6.75
	0.300	1.64	8.20
b	0.010	1.51	2.00
	0.020	1.54	2.85
	0.050	1.56	4.45
	0.100	1.59	6.20
	0.200	1.64	9.20
	0.300	1.68	10.90
c	0.010	1.53	1.50
	0.020	1.56	2.20
	0.050	1.59	3.35
	0.100	1.62	4.65
	0.200	1.66	6.80
	0.300	1.71	8.20
d	0.010	1.54	1.80
	0.020	1.57	2.65
	0.050	1.59	4.20
	0.100	1.61	5.60
	0.200	1.66	8.25
	0.300	1.70	10.35
e	0.010	1.42	2.00
	0.020	1.44	2.85
	0.050	1.47	4.45
	0.100	1.50	6.20
	0.200	1.54	9.25
	0.300	1.59	11.00

the decrease in current with time, and the number of electrons per molecule was computed from $i-t$ curves following the procedure outlined by Lingane¹⁰ and found to be four. After disconnecting the electrolysis cell, 1 ml of the resulting solution was withdrawn and presence of aromatic amine in this solution was revealed by the standard spot test¹¹. The remaining reaction mixture was partially evaporated on a water-bath to half its volume, allowed to cool to room temperature and extracted with ether. The ether layer was evaporated under diminished pressure and the yellow crystalline solid was identified as 3-methyl-4-amino-2-isoxazolin-5-one (Found : C, 41.7; H, 4.9; N, 23.5. $C_4H_6N_2O_2$ requires : C, 42.1; H, 5.3; N, 24.56%); v_{max} (KBr) 1 590 (C=N), 1 675

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 3-methyl-4-(benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-one (1×10^{-3} M) in aqueous dimethylformamide (50%, v/v) at (a) pH* 3.66 and (b) pH* 7.66; scan rate = $0.100 V s^{-1}$.

(C=O cyclic), 3 255 (NH), 3 010 (C-CH₃), 1 470 and 1 430 cm^{-1} (heterocyclic ring).

Structural effects : The parameters α_n , $d\Delta E_{1/2}/d \Delta pH$ and I (diffusion current constant) lie practically in the same range for all the members of the reaction series. Thus it is possible to apply the Hammett's relation to the series. For this purpose substituent constants σ used were taken from the literature¹². $E_{1/2}$ is plotted against Hammett substituent constant in Britton-Robinson buffer of pH* 3.66 (Fig. 2). It is observed from the plots that electron-withdrawing groups shifts the $E_{1/2}$ towards

TABLE 5—MILLICOULOMETRIC RESULTS ON 3-METHYL-4-(BENZENEAZO)-2-ISOXAZOLIN-5-ONE AT pH 3.66

Concn. = 1×10^{-3} M (1ml)			
Current μA	Time s	n -value	
7.0	0	—	
6.1	7200	3.8	
5.8	10800	4.1	

Fig. 2. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs σ_p .

more positive values. Further, $E_{1/2}$ vs σ plot is linear. The correlation coefficient calculated for $E_{1/2}$ vs σ plot ($r = 1.0$) show satisfactory application of the Hammett's correlation to the system under study. The positive ρ value suggests that the nucleophilic reaction is rate-determining. The positive ρ value thus suggests that electron-addition step is more important. The results also suggest that the presence of substituents does not affect the mechanism of reduction of the present compounds but only makes the reduction either easy or difficult depending on the nature of the substituent.

Mechanism : Based on the results obtained, the mechanisms shown in Schemes 1 and 2 are suggested for the electroreduction of 3-methyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)-2-isoxazolin-5-ones (1). The mechanisms are consistent with the earlier mechanisms suggested for the reduction of other azomethine groups¹³.

Experimental

Compounds **1a-e** were prepared by the reported method¹⁴. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc. Stock solutions of the compounds were prepared in dimethyl-

Scheme 2. Reduction pattern in alkaline solutions

formamide (A.R.). Britton-Robinson buffers¹⁵ were prepared and used.

Procedure : Polarograms were recorded for deaerated solution containing the stock solution (1 ml) of the compounds, DMF (4 ml; the minimum volume to keep the compound in solution) and buffer solution of desired pH (5 ml). Before recording the polarograms the pH value of the experimental solutions was measured against a pH^* standard buffer¹⁶ solution containing 50% aqueous-DMF, in order to find out the operational pH values of the experimental solutions in 50% aqueous dimethylformamide solution. These pH values are now considered as pH^* values. The current-voltage curves were recorded in the potential range 0.0–2.0 V vs SCE. The number of electrons involved in the reduction process was determined

by millicoulometry using CdSO_4 as the reference solution.

The description of the instruments employed in the present studies was given earlier¹⁷

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.V.R.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance and also to Dr. C. Sheshaiah, Reader in Mathematics, M. K. University, Madurai for his help during the course of his research work.

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